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The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, BOPO (Operational Costs, Operational Income), and Non-Profit/Loss Operations on Murabahah Receivables with Firm Size as a Moderation Variable in Islamic Banking in Indonesia Period of 2018-2023

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Abstract

This research is aimed at analyzing the impact of Zakat, Infaq, Sadaqah, Waqf (ZISWAF), Operational Costs, Operational Income (BOPO), and Non-Operating Profit/Loss (NOPL) on Murabahah Financials with Firm Size as a moderating variable for the period from Year 2015.Q1 to 2023.Q3. This research uses quantitative methods with multiple regression models to test hypotheses. The research results show that ZIS, BOPO, and NOPL have a significant positive impact on Financial Murabahah, while Firms Size has a significant negative impact on Financial Murabahah. This research provides empirical evidence regarding the impact of ZIS, BOPO, and NOPL with Financial Murabahah and the moderating effect of Company Size. The results of this research can be useful for financial institutions and governments to understand the factors that influence Financial Murabahah and to develop strategies to promote this financial instrument.

Keywords: ZISWAF, BOPO, Non-Operational Profit/Loss, Murabahah Receivables, Firm Size

INTRODUCTION

The sharia banking industry in Indonesia has shown significant growth in recent years. This growth is in line with Islamic economic principles which prioritize justice and shared prosperity. Sharia banking, which operates in accordance with Islamic law, offers an alternative for people who want a financial system that is free from elements of usury, gharar and maysir. The main focus of Islamic banks is on financing and collecting funds in accordance with sharia contracts, as well as contributing to social functions through managing zakat, infaq, alms and waqf funds (Tuzzuhro et al., 2023) .

One of the challenges faced by Islamic banks is managing financing risk, including the risk of bad murabahah receivables. Uncollectible murabahah receivables can be measured through the non-performing receivables ratio or Non-Performing Financing (NPF). On the other hand, Islamic banks also face challenges in optimizing the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakat, Infaq, Sadaqah, Waqf) funds and managing Operational Costs against Operational Income (BOPO), as well as maximizing Non-Operational Profit/Loss. Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds and effective management of BOPO can have a positive impact on the bank's financial performance, while Non-Operational Profit/Loss can be a source of additional income or reduced costs (Hartini, 2016) . In September 2023, OJK recorded that total sharia banking assets reached IDR 831.95 trillion, growing 10.94 percent from the same period last year with a market share of 7.27 percent. The performance of sharia banking shows a positive trend, reflecting that public trust in sharia banking is getting stronger. In December 2023, total sharia banking

assets will reach IDR 892.2 trillion, growing 11.21% YoY. Fundraising also recorded positive performance. Sharia banking deposits rose IDR 65 trillion to IDR 684.5 trillion, or grew 10.49% YoY. The market share of sharia banking deposits in national banking deposits was recorded at 7.9%. The health level of sharia banking is well maintained during the COVID-19 pandemic. The CAR ratio was recorded at 25.41% in December 2023, slightly lower than the BOPO ratio of the national banking industry. This growth is driven by improvements in infrastructure and digital access services, as well as increasing public trust in sharia banking products (Wahyuningsih & Gunawan, 2017). Sharia banking offers an alternative for people who want a financial system that is free from elements of usury, gharar and maysir. The main focus of sharia banks is on financing and collecting funds in accordance with sharia contracts, as well as contributing to social functions through managing zakat, infaq, alms and waqf funds. Company size or firm size is an important factor that can moderate the influence of ZISWAF fund receipts, BOPO, and Non-Operational Profit/Loss on murabahah receivables. Therefore, this research aims to analyze the effect of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, BOPO, and Non-Operational Profit/Loss on murabahah receivables by considering firm size as a moderating variable during the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3.

THEORETICAL STUDY

of Zakat, Infaq, Shodaqoh, & Waqf (ZISWAF)

Zakat, Infaq, Shodaqoh, and Waqf (ZISWAF) is a form of philanthropy in Islam which aims to reduce social disparities and advance community economic activities (Widiastuti et al., 2022). Zakat is a form of obligatory charity that is based on a certain calculation of wealth and is one of the five pillars of Islam (Syakir et al., 2021). Infaq refers to voluntary giving outside the obligation of zakat, while alms is a general term for voluntary acts of charity. Waqf is dedicating property or assets for religious or charitable purposes, with the resulting income used for the benefit of society.

Operating Expenses Operating Income (BOPO)

Operating Expenses Operating Income (BOPO) is a ratio/parameter that measures a company's operational costs in relation to operational income (Wahyuningsih & Gunawan, 2017). This ratio is characterized by the accumulation of operating costs and profits. A higher BOPO ratio indicates that the company is more efficient in managing its operational costs, which can increase profitability (Al-Mana et al., 2020). BOPO is the main factor for determining the profitability of a company, especially in the banking sector, where it can influence Return on Assets (ROA) and other financial performance indicators.

Non-Operating Profit and Loss (LRNO)

Non-Operational Labor Laws (LRNO) are a type of law that focuses on the profits or gains that companies derive from their activities outside of their regular business operations (Lyanda, 2021). This may reduce investments, income, or profit margins in the short term, and lower other costs. Non-Operating Income is also referred to as intra- or interpersonal payments. It is important for investors to understand the difference between operational and non-operating profit margins because it provides clearer information about a company's efficiency and profitability. Non-operating income is usually recorded at the bottom of a company's income statement, meaning that those using financial statements can limit business activities to arising in the top part of the income statement only. For example, non-operating profits include dividends, gains or

losses on investments, and gains or losses arising from market fluctuations and depreciation of asset prices.

Firm Size

Company size refers to the scale of a business organization, usually measured by the number of employees, total revenue, or added value (Yanuarita, 2022). A company's size can have significant implications for its operations, efficiency, and competitiveness. For example, larger companies can benefit from economies of scale, which allow them to produce goods and services more efficiently due to increased purchasing power and their ability to invest in advanced technology. However, there are also limits to company size, as larger organizations may face challenges such as bureaucratic inefficiencies, coordination costs, and regulatory constraints.

Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on Murabahah Receivables (H1)

The Effect of Zakat, Infaq, Shodaqoh and Waqf on Murabahah Financing is handled by the Effect of Receipt of Zakat, Infaq, Shodaqoh and Waqf Funds (ZISWAF). Monetary swapping is a type of sharia swap where a bank buys an item from a savings bank and then sells it back to the savings bank at a higher price, with the difference between the two prices being a profit for the bank (Almsafir & Alsmadi, 2014). As sources of funds in sharia finance, zakat, infaq, shodaqoh, and waqf are supported by these conditions and limits. Receipt of these funds may impair the bank's ability to provide loans at reasonable interest rates because the money may be used to comply with sharia requirements or be subject to certain situations. The impact of these fees on mortgage refinancing may vary depending on the current situation and the loan repayment rate.

Effect of BOPO on Murabahah Receivables (H2)

BOPO is a cost that arises from the operational activities of an organization. This includes costs such as legal, accounting, utilities, and other costs incurred when starting a business (Wahyuningsih & Gunawan, 2017). When BOPO reaches a certain level, it will reduce the company's profits, which will ultimately affect profitability and the ability to pay Murabahah Receivables. As a result, more BOPOs may lead to an increase in Murabahah Receivables as businesses may need to withhold payments from customers to meet their obligations. Conversely, more BOPOs may result in higher Murabahah Receivables because the company may have more cash available to pay customers quickly. That is why the relationship between BOPO and Murabahah Receivables is quite complex and can have a significant impact on the financial productivity of employees within the company.

Influence of Non-Operational Profit/Loss on Murabahah Receivables (H3)

The effect of non-operating profit/loss on murabahah relates to how non-operating profit/ambition can affect murabahah. In the currency cycle, murabahah receivables are expressed in a simple way in the currency position consolidation cycle (Lyanda, 2021). Non-operational profit/loss, such as the difference between actual value and estimated customer value, is called profit/loss. If the vehicle price is more expensive than the financing receivable balance, then the option is classified as a profit or loss. In the process of selling baby goods, consumers offer incentives to Subsidiaries to sell their own products or to buy other goods if there are weaknesses in the purchasing process. If the

collateral price is greater than the financing receivable balance, and compared with other comprehension tests that will be evaluated in the laboratory before the test, the number of Comprehension tests will be reduced.

Firm Size Moderates ZISWAF Fund Receipts Against Murabahah Receivables (H4)

Firm Size has the ability to moderate the relationship between ZISWAF (Zakat, Infaq, Alms, Waqf) and murabahah receivables in the sharia banking industry. Larger Islamic banks have more power and network power, enabling them to manage and use ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds more effectively. As a result, a decrease in ZISWAF payments due to higher default rates may be more significant for banks with larger portfolios. Similarly, smaller Islamic banks are more likely to experience difficulties when transferring funds from ZISWAF to mortgages due to low deposits and network infrastructure (Munandar et al., 2021). This is related to research conducted by Arfionita & Sa'adati (2023) which found that the size of a company affects the current asset ratio (CAR), operational profitability (BOPO), and share price.

Firm Size Moderates BOPO on Murabahah Receivables (H5)

Company size has the potential to moderate the relationship between operational profitability (BOPO) and cash flow in the Islamic finance industry. Larger Islamic banks have more resources and networks that enable them to engage and use BOPO more efficiently. As a result, the impact of BOPO on interest rates may be more significant for banks with larger balances. Smaller Islamic banks may experience difficulties in implementing BOPO due to limited resources and networks. Therefore, larger Islamic banks may be more effective in using BOPO funds to increase profit margins, whereas smaller Islamic banks may face difficulties in doing so. This is consistent with research conducted by Arfionita & Sa'adati (2023) which found that companies manage the impact of the Current Asset Ratio (CAR), Balance of Payment Outstanding (BOPO), and the Federal Reserve Rate on their income. In this case, firm size can be a moderating variable that influences how Islamic banks use BOPO to increase murabahah receivables.

Firm Size Moderates Non-Operational Profit and Loss on Murabahah Receivables (H6)

Company size has the ability to moderate the relationship between non-operating profit and loss and murabahah receivables in the sharia banking industry. Larger Islamic banks have more branches and network infrastructure, which allows them to use non-operational lending laboratories more effectively. Given this, bank-to-bank variations in deposit sizes may be more significant when considering non-operational laboratory results. Smaller Islamic banks may experience difficulties in completing non-operational laboratory work due to resource and network disruptions. As a result, larger Islamic banks tend to be more effective in using non-operational laboratories to increase murabahah receivables, whereas small Islamic banks may have difficulty in carrying out this task. Related to research conducted by Arfionita & Sa'adati (2023) which states that the size of an organization influences the effects of the Current Asset Ratio (CAR), Balance of Payment Outstanding (BOPO), and fed rate on loan payments. This means that business size can be a moderating variable that influences how a sharia bank uses non-operating profits and losses to increase murabahah receivables.

Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, BOPO, and Non-Operational Profit/Loss on Murabahah Receivables (H7)

ZISWAF fund receipts, BOPO, and non-operating profit/loss play an important role in

determining the level of murabahah receivables in the Islamic finance industry. Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, which consist of donations from the community and charity funds, can provide additional capital for sharia banks to provide murabahah financing to customers. An increase in ZISWAF fund receipts can increase the sources of funds available for financing, thereby increasing the potential for growth in murabahah receivables (Gani, 2023) . Apart from that, BOPO (Operational and Marketing Costs) also has a significant influence on murabahah receivables. Low operational costs can increase the bank's ability to provide more financing, which in turn can increase murabahah receivables. Non-operating profit/loss also affects murabahah receivables, because profits earned can be used to increase sources of funds available for financing, while losses can reduce the bank's ability to provide financing. In synthesis, receipt of ZISWAF, BOPO funds and non-operational profit/loss have a significant influence on murabahah receivables in the sharia financial industry, with receipt of ZISWAF and BOPO funds increasing the potential for growth in murabahah receivables and non-operational profit/loss which affects the bank's ability to provide financing.

The following is a correlation between the research independent variable and the research dependent variable presented in the conceptual framework:

Figure 1. Research conceptual framework

Source: Processed by the author (2024)

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative approach, using second class data collection originating from the reporting company's website as well as idx.co.id. The sample population for this study consists of companies in the financial sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) during the 2020-2022 period. The sample selection technique used in this research is intensive sampling, with a sample size of 50 companies in the financial sector each year, which means that the overall sample size is small. The data analysis techniques used in this research include panel data regression analysis and moderate regression analysis. (MRA). According to Ghozali (2018) & Cahyani et al., (2024) , an analytical approach that maintains sample integrity and responds to this approach is a basic method for assessing the influence of moderator variables for interaction tests or moderated regression analysis. Model comparisons in panel data regression analysis are as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Murabahah Receivables

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X 1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

X 2 = BOPO

X 3 = Profit and Loss

e_i = Error

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using regression analysis involving moderating variables through Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA). The regression equation used includes interaction elements with the following equation formula:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 Z + \beta_5$$

Where:

Y = Murabahah Receivables

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X 1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

X 2 = BOPO

X 3 = Profit and Loss

Z = Firm Size

X 1 *Z = Multiplicative interaction between receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds and firm size

X 2 *Z = Multiplicative interaction between NPF Nett and firm size

X 3 *Z = Multiplicative interaction between musyarakah income and firm size

e_i = Error

RESEARCH RESULT

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

According to Table 1, there are 115 samples of Sharia General Banking businesses listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange during the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. Some descriptive statistical results are presented in Table 1 for the institutional variable (X1). This variable has the following values: mean = 0.739600, median = 0.790000, maximum = 0.990000,

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	25082.01	90.86165	-7569.826	15605238	14.31333
Median	18,00000	94.91000	70,00000	2747334	14.82614
Maximum	669879.0	202.7400	148455.0	1.34E+08	18.70994
Minimum	0.000000	64.64000	-133641.0	12930.00	9.467305
Std. Dev.	87500.44	14.72556	35190.66	32580117	2.643193
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

minimum = 0.210000, and standard deviation = 0.190315.

In the structural mode variable (X2), the descriptive statistical results in Table 4.1 present the variable, which is based on the debt to equity ratio and has an average value of 3.015467 median 2.620.000, 10.81000 maximum, 0.000000 minimum, and 2.381843 deviation.

The profitability variable (Z), which is determined by applying the general Return on Assets method, has the values 0.025933, 0.020000, 0.410000 as the maximum, 0.000000 as the minimum, and 0.043243 as the deviation.

The results of descriptive statistical analysis in Table 4.1 show that the average variable Y, as determined by Tobin's Q, has a value of 1.020200, 0.940000 for median, 3.450000 for maximum, 0.080000 for minimum, and 0.496335 for deviation.

Selection of Panel Data Regression Models

Selection of a panel data regression model is an analysis stage to determine the best method between Common Effect, Fixed Effect or Random Effect.

1. Chow Test

This test was carried out to determine the best model between the Common Effect Model (CEM) and the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Table 2. Chow Test Results

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests			
Equation: Untitled			
Cross-section fixed effects test			
Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	10.666906	-4,106	0
Chi-square cross-section	38.901511	4	0

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 2, the Chow test results show that the chi-square cross-section probability value is $0.0000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that the best model used in this test is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

2. Hausman test

The Hausman test aims to determine the best model between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Random Effect Model (REM).

Table 3. Hausman Test Results

Correlated Random Effects-Hausman Test			
Equation: Untitled			
Cross-section random effects test			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
Random cross-section	42.667624	4	0

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 3, the Hausman test results show that the probability value is $0.0000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that the best model used in this test is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Classical Assumption Test

1. Normality Test

Table 4. Normality Test

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on Figure 4 above, the probability value is 0.00000, which means the probability value is below 0.05 ($0.0000 < 0.05$). So it can be concluded that the data in this study is not normally distributed.

2. Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 5. Heteroscedasticity Test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	-955686.9	90357.88	-10.57669	0
X1	6.807492	21.93526	0.310345	0.7569
X2	767,567	669,268	1.146875	0.2539
X3	6.51782	5.870427	1.11028	0.2693
Z	89453.8	6123.609	14.60802	0

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 6, the results of the heteroscedasticity test show that the calculated probabilities are less than 0.05, except for constant (c) and moderation (z). Each regression model will be based on heteroscedasticity if it has a probability value greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that the regression model used in this study does not show heteroscedasticity.

Panel Data Regression Analysis

The following is a panel data regression analysis using the best model, namely the Fixed Effect Model regression:

Table 6. Fixed Effect Model Panel Data Regression Analysis

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	106.2408	20.21009	5.25682	0
X2	-231574.8	88122.55	-2.627872	0.0099
X3	-249,347	53.07219	-4.698262	0
Z	9490774	1779755	5.332629	0
C	-1.04E+08	26407511	-3.92882	0.0002
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.86734	Mean dependent var	15605238	
Adjusted R-squared	0.857328	SD dependent var	32580117	
SE of regression	12306128	Akaike info criterion	35.56412	
Sum squared resid	1.61E+16	Schwarz criterion	35.77894	
Log likelihood	-2035,937	Hannan-Quinn Criter.	35.65132	
F-statistic	86.62971	Durbin-Watson stat	1.483622	
Prob(F-statistic)	0			

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Moderated Regression Analysis (Moderated Regression Analysis-MRA)

Moderating variables can be defined as variables that are able to establish or maintain a relationship between independent and dependent variables. The following are the results of moderate regression analysis:

Table 7. Moderation Regression Analysis Test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	-2873.028	961.9514	-2.986666	0.0035
X2	2755494	390859.5	7.049833	0
X3	1255.261	327.3047	3.835144	0.0002
Z	28114774	3136330	8.964227	0
X1Z	157.7177	52.38165	3.010935	0.0033
X2Z	-240786.6	32123.29	-7.495704	0
X3Z	-87.19389	20.13972	-4.329449	0
C	-3.30E+08	39018472	-8.45507	0

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Statistical Test

1. T test

The t test is used to determine whether the dependent variable has a statistically significant effect on the independent variable. Apart from that, this test is also used to determine whether the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable is tested at a significance level of 0.05 or a confidence level of 95% and an error rate of 5%.

Table 8. T Test Results

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	-2873.028	961.9514	-2.986666	0.0035
X2	2755494	390859.5	7.049833	0
X3	1255.261	327.3047	3.835144	0.0002
Z	28114774	3136330	8.964227	0
X1Z	157.7177	52.38165	3.010935	0.0033
X2Z	-240786.6	32123.29	-7.495704	0
X3Z	-87.19389	20.13972	-4.329449	0
C	-3.30E+08	39018472	-8.45507	0

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

Based on the t test (partial) carried out in this research, the results are as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has an impact on Murabahah Receivables. With a coefficient of -2873.028 and a probability of 0.0035, which is less than the 0.5 or 5% significance level. This means that ZISWAF's profits have increased compared to Syariah Bank Murabahah for the period 2018Q1-2023Q3.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): BOPO affects Murabahah Receivables. Coefficient: 2755494 and Probability: 0.0000 0035, indicating a significance level lower than 0.5 or 5%. This provides evidence that Operational Costs have an impact on Sharia Bank Murabahah from 2018Q1 to 2023Q3.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Non-operative losses have an impact on murabahah receivables. With a coefficient of 1255.261 and a probability of 0.0002 0035, it provides a significance level lower than 0.5 or 5%. This shows that Non-Operational Profit and Loss has a positive impact on Sharia Banking Murabahah.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): The impact of Ziswaf data on P. Murrabahah depends on solid size. Coefficient: 157.7177, Probability: 0.0033, indicating a significance level lower than 0.5 or 5%. This means that Firm Size moderates the impact of GCG control variables on sharia bank deposits.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): BOPO has an impact on pricing based on company size. With a coefficient of -240786.6 and a probability of 0.0000, which is less than the 0.5 or 5% significance level. This shows that Company Size can reduce the impact of BOPO on Sharia Banking Murabahah between 2018Q1 and 2023Q3.

Hypothesis 6 (H6): Non-operating Profit and Loss has an impact on Murabahah in companies of different sizes. With a coefficient of -87.19389 and a probability of 0.0000,

which is less than the 0.5 or 5% significance level. This shows that Firm Size can reduce the impact of Non-Operational Profit and Loss on Sharia Banking Murabahah during 2018Q1-2023Q3.

Hypothesis 7 (H7): Income from ZISWAF, BOPO, and Non-Operative Laboratories have a simultaneous impact on Murabahah.

2. F Test

The F test is used to test whether the independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on the dependent variable. Following are the results of the F test:

Table 9. F Test Results

R-squared	0.949078	Mean dependent var	15605238
Adjusted R-squared	0.943639	SD dependent var	32580117
SE of regression	7734658	Akaike info criterion	34.65881
Sum squared resid	6.16E+15	Schwarz criterion	34.94524
Log likelihood	-1980,882	Hannan-Quinn Criter.	34.77507
F-statistic	174.5167	Durbin-Watson stat	1.334952
Prob(F-statistic)	0		

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

In this study, F is used at a significance level of 0.05 or 5%, with the criterion that if $F < 0.05$, the regression coefficient is suitable for use. The F results in Table 9 show a value of 0.000000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. As a result, it can be concluded that ZISWAF, BOPO, and Non-Operational Profit/Loss Funds influence company size.

3. Coefficient of Determination Test

The Coefficient of Determination is used to determine how much the independent variable contributes to the regression model when explaining the variable from the dependent variable.

Table 10. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

R-squared	0.949078	Mean dependent var	15605238
Adjusted R-squared	0.943639	SD dependent var	32580117
SE of regression	7734658	Akaike info criterion	34.65881
Sum squared resid	6.16E+15	Schwarz criterion	34.94524
Log likelihood	-1980,882	Hannan-Quinn Criter.	34.77507
F-statistic	174.5167	Durbin-Watson stat	1.334952
Prob(F-statistic)	0		

Source: Eviews 12 (Data processed by the author)

According to Table 10, the panel data regression results with Murabahah Receivables as

the dependent variable show that the Adjusted R2 value is 0.943639. This means that 94.36% of the variance in Murabahah Receivables can be explained by ZISWAF, BOPO, and Non-Operational Profit/Loss. Apart from that, it can be explained using other variables outside the regression model.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on Murabahah Receivables

According to Table 8, the probability of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds is 0.0035, which is less than the threshold of 0.05. The test also shows a negative trend with a coefficient of -2873.028 and a t-statistic of -2.986666. This shows the negative impact of ZISWAF income on murabahah receivables. As a result, the hypothesis H1 that ZISWAF Fund Receipts have an impact on Murabahah Receivables has been accepted.

The results of this research are consistent with previous research conducted by Mohsin (2013). From the research results it can be concluded that ZISWAF funding has a negative impact on Murabahah Receivables. In particular, a hypothesis about the impact of ZISWAF income on Murabahah receivables is proposed.

The Effect of BOPO on Murabahah Receivables

Based on table 8, the results show that the probability of BOPO is 0.0000, which is less than 0.05. The test also shows a positive trend with a coefficient of 2,755,494 and a t statistic of 7.049833. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that BOPO has a positive effect on Murabahah Receivables, therefore Hypothesis 2 (H2) is accepted.

This is consistent with previous research by Zulkhairi (2021) , which found that operational productivity and expenses from bank operations can increase bank profitability. BOPO is one of the methods used by banks to reduce operational risk, which therefore has an impact on bank activities. The BOPO ratio is used as an indicator to assess a bank's ability and efficiency in carrying out operational activities.

The Effect of Non-Operational Profit and Loss on Murabahah Receivables

According to Table 8, the research results show that the probability of non-operative profit and loss is 0.0002, which is less than 0.05. The results also show a positive trend with a coefficient of 1255.261 and a t-statistic of 3.835144. This shows that Non-Operational Profit and Loss has a positive impact on Murabahah. The hypothesis proposed by the researchers, Hypothesis 3 (H3), is that Non-Operational Loss has an impact on Murabahah.

The findings of this research are consistent with previous research by Anggraini (2022) and Pertiwi (2021) which found that receiving cheap, mudharabah, musyarakah, and multi-service ijarah had a positive impact on net profit. Mudarabah, musyarakah, and multiservice ijarah are different types of developments, but they all have a positive impact on net profit.

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on Murabahah Receivables with Firm Size as Moderation

Based on Table 8, the results show that the interaction probability between ZISWAF and Firm Size is 0.0033, which is less than 0.05. The results show a positive trend with a coefficient of 157.7177 and a t-statistic of 3.010935. This shows that company size can influence the relationship between ZISWAF income and murabahah receivables. Thus,

the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, Hypothesis 4 (H4), is that ZISWAF revenue has an impact on company size.

The findings from this research also support previous research by Hanim (2021) which stated that the implementation of zakat has a positive and significant impact on profitability. Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can have a positive impact on murabahah receivables because zakat can be used to reduce investment costs and increase bank productivity.

The Effect of BOPO on Murabahah Receivables with Firm Size as Moderation

Based on table 8, the results show that the interaction probability between BOPO and Firm Size is 0.0000, which is less than 0.05. The results show a negative trend with a coefficient of -240786.6 and a t statistic of -7.495704. This shows that company size has an impact on BOPO. Thus, the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, Hypothesis 5 (H5): BOPO has an effect on Murabahah Receivables moderated by Firm Size, has been accepted.

Previous research by Fadlyanti (2023) Migra et al. (2021) Saputri & Arinta (2021) found a positive relationship between BOPO (Operating Costs and Operating Income) and murabahah receivables, but the size was not significant. This may seem contradictory to Hypothesis 5 which states a negative influence, but what needs to be paid attention to here is the moderating variable, not the independent variable on the dependent variable. The Influence of Non-Operational Profit and Loss on Murabahah Receivables with Firm Size as Moderation

According to Table 8, the interaction probability between Non-Operational Profit and Loss and Firm Size is 0.0000, which is less than 0.05. The results also show a negative value with a coefficient of -87.19389 and a t statistic of -4.329449. This shows that the relationship between Non-Operational Profit and Loss and Murabahah Receivables is influenced by company size. The hypothesis chosen by the researchers, Hypothesis 6 (H6), is that Non-Operational Loss has an impact on Murabahah in Moderation of Company Size.

The Impact of Non-Operating Profit and Loss on Murabahah Receivables with Firm Size as Moderation is complex and can be positive or negative depending on market conditions and fluctuations. Research by Saputri & Arinta (2021) found that cheap housing has no impact on financial performance. However, Fariza's research (2022) shows that the development of murabahah has a positive and significant impact on the profitability of Indonesian Islamic banks. Other research has found that receiving murabahah, mudharabah, musyarakah, and multiservices has a positive impact on net profit. However, musharaka receipts have no impact on laboratory operations because they are offset by receipts of other products or services.

The Effect of Simultaneous Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, BOPO and Non-Operational Profit and Loss on Murabahah Receivables

Based on the data in Table 9, it can be concluded that the variables ZISWAF, BOPO, and Non-Operational Profit and Loss have a significant impact on Murabahah Receivables. The result is a significance level of $0.00000 < 0.05$. The results show that ZISWAF Fund Receipts, BOPO, and Non-Operational Losses have a simultaneous negative impact on Murabahah Receivables. Thus, the research hypothesis, which is Hypothesis 7 (H7): Simultaneous Effects of ZISWAF, BOPO, and Non-Operational Loss on Murabahah Receivables, is formulated.

R Square or coefficient of determination produces a value of 0.949078. Interpretation of this graph shows that the contribution of the two basic variables is 94.90%, with the remaining 5.10% influenced by other factors. Therefore, other independent variables can be used for further research.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, there is a significant influence of ZISWAF fund receipts, BOPO, and non-operational profit/loss on murabahah receivables in sharia banking. This is evidenced by the negative coefficient value and probability below 5%, indicating the statistical significance of this effect. Furthermore, firm size acts as a significant moderating variable, with a positive coefficient and probability below 5%, indicating that firm size influences the relationship between ZISWAF, BOPO, and non-operating profit/loss with murabahah receivables.

Practical Implications: These findings provide important insights for Islamic financial institutions in managing murabahah receivables and determining appropriate strategies to improve financial performance. In particular, understanding the role of firm size can help in making more effective strategic decisions. **Recommendations for Further Research,** This research can be used as a basis for further, more in-depth studies regarding the factors that influence murabahah receivables and the role of other moderating variables in sharia banking. **Research Contribution,** This research adds empirical evidence to the existing literature regarding the impact of ZISWAF, BOPO, and non-operating profit/loss on murabahah receivables, and reveals the importance of firm size as a moderating variable in this context.

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